

Law, AI and robotics: France

[WP4 – AI and robotics]

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Abstract

This report reviews the state of the law and current legal responses to technological developments in AI and robotics. It also explores how specific questions and issues are addressed in France: the issue of algorithmic bias, intellectual property of works created by AI, the creation of a specific legal status for robots and, finally, safety and civil liability issues for damages caused by robots.

Developments in AI and robotics challenge the existing legal framework, pose new questions, and create new issues. More profoundly, they challenge a fundamental distinction in French law, the one between the *subject* of law (as a physical or a legal person) and the *object* of law. The question related to the legal status of autonomous systems is therefore key in the current debate in France on the legal regulation of AI and robotics. This has, in turn, repercussions on the way intellectual property of AI is regulated as well as on safety and civil liability issues.

At the moment, highly sophisticated automated systems (so called “smart” systems) are not given a specific legal status. Only a few legal experts support the creation of a legal personality for such systems. The majority of French experts today believe that the *summa divisio* of French law between the subject of right and the object of right is not to be currently challenged.

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Table of contents

Abstract	2
Table of contents	3
Executive summary	4
List of tables	6
List of acronyms/abbreviations	6
Glossary of terms	6
1. Introduction	8
2. Scope and limitations of the report	10
3. Legal developments	11
4. Specific legal issues	15
4.1. Artificial intelligence	16
4.1.1. Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems)	16
4.1.2. Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI	17
4.2. Robotics	19
4.2.1. Creation of a specific legal status for robots	19
4.2.2. Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?	21
5. Brief analysis of gaps and challenges	22
6. Conclusion	23
References	25

Executive summary

The objective of this report is to review current legal responses to technological developments in artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics and determine how specific questions and legal issues are addressed in France. It also looks at how the law might evolve in the future in relation to developments in AI and robotics. It also introduces key aspects of the ongoing French debate on the legal regulation of these technologies as evident in current legal academic literature.

Currently, there is no specific law regulating AI or robotics in France. Nonetheless, some pre-existing laws address a number of key issues related to these technologies, in particular the law n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 regarding information technology, files and liberties as modified by the law n°2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 that integrates the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) with national legislation.

The rapid technological developments that have taken place in AI and robotics over the last 10 years approximately have generated much interest from policy-makers in France; this is reflected by the number of high-level reports published recently and analysed in this report.

Developments in AI and robotics challenge the existing legal framework, pose new questions, and create new issues. More profoundly, they challenge a fundamental distinction in French law, the one between the *subject* of law (as a physical or a legal person) and the *object* of law. Some legal experts and lawyers in France today enthusiastically support the creation of new legal categories to provide a legal framework for these emerging technologies, including through the recognition of the autonomous system as a subject of right, and not simply as an object, as it is the case today. The lawyer Alain Bensoussan is a particularly vocal proponent of this evolution.¹ A number of legal experts are against this legal development, arguing that the legal distinction between the object and the subject should never be challenged as it is justified by the very nature of the entities at stake (such as for Xavier Labbé²). Others argue that it is still too early to move in the direction of such profound transformation of the very structure of French law (such as for Alexandra Bensamoun and Grégoire Loiseau³). For these experts, solutions to questions and issues raised by AI and robotics can and should be addressed with the already existing legal regulatory frameworks.

This report starts by introducing recent legal changes in France in relation to technological development in AI and robotics. Considering the rapidly evolving technologies and regulatory responses, the report focuses on the past five to ten years and points to potential future legal developments. It then explores more precisely two specific legal issues that are posed by each of these two technologies. For AI, it starts by looking at how automatic decision-making is regulated in French law and then explores issues related to intellectual property. For robotics, the key issues of the creation of a specific legal status for robots as well as safety and civil liability issues are addressed.

Finally, it discusses some existing gaps and challenges in the current legal regulation of AI and robotics in France, in particular the focus on soft law responses (i.e., ethical responses) to current regulatory

¹ Bensoussan, Alain, "Droit Des Robots : Science-Fiction Ou Anticipation ?", *Recueil Dalloz*, 2015, p. 1640.

² Labbé, Pascal, 'L'homme Augmenté à l'épreuve de La Distinction Des Personnes et Des Choses', in *L'homme Augmenté Face Au Droit*, Xavier Labbé (ed.), Villeneuve d'Ascq, 2015, p. 47. Quote in the original French language: "le robot n'aura jamais la personnalité juridique... Il lui manque 'l'âme'".

³ Bensamoun, Alexandra, and Grégoire Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2017, p. 239.

issues of these technologies (as opposed to a response from hard laws). It also shows/discusses how the current legal response to the risks posed by AI and robotics tends to focus on the individual and, as such, misses addressing the impacts of these technologies at the collective (group) level.

List of tables

- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations
- **Table 2:** Glossary of terms

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial intelligence
Art	Article
CDPA	Copyright, Designs and Patents Act
CGE	General Council of Economy (<i>Conseil Général de l'Economie</i>)
CNIL	National Council for Information Technologies and Liberties (<i>Conseil National de l'Informatique et des Libertés</i>)
CNNum	National Digital Council (<i>Conseil National du Numérique</i>)
D	Deliverable
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICESCR	International Covenant on Social, Economic and Cultural Rights
IMT	Mines Telecom Institute (<i>Institut Mines Télécoms</i>)
INRIA	National Research Institute in informatics technology and automatic systems (<i>Institut National de Recherche en Sciences du Numérique</i>)
IP	Intellectual Property
IT	Information Technology
SYMOP	Professional organisation of creators of industrial solutions, producers of machines, technologies and equipment for industrial production
UN	United Nations
WP	Work package

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Artificial intelligence	The science and engineering of machines with capabilities that are considered intelligent (i.e., intelligent by the standard of <i>human</i> intelligence). Major applications of AI technology are in transportation, education, finance, industry, healthcare, marketing, management, telecommunications, entertainment and defence, amongst other fields. Important subfields of AI were found to include: knowledge representation and automated reasoning, artificial neural networks, machine learning, computer vision, computer audition, natural language processing, expert systems, data mining, intelligent agent systems and automated planning, evolutionary computation. [SIENNA D4.1]

Term	Explanation
Robotics	The field of science and engineering that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots. Major applications of robots are in transportation, industry, healthcare, education, entertainment, space exploration, defence, retail, companionship, housekeeping and other areas. Important subfields of robotics were found to include: robot mechanics, robot sensing, robot control (including many subareas, such as robot learning, adaptive control, developmental robotics, evolutionary robotics, cognitive robotics, behaviour-based robotics, robotic mapping and planning), robot locomotion, bio-inspired and soft robotics, humanoid robotics, microrobotics, nanorobotics, beam robotics, cloud robotics, swarm robotics, telerobotics, social robotics and human-robot interaction. [SIENNA D4.1]
Automated decision-making	Decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning a data subject or similarly significantly affects him or her (GDPR, Article 22 (1)). It refers to individual decision-making made by automated means without any human involvement. Examples include: an online decision to award a loan; and a recruitment aptitude test which uses pre-programmed algorithms and criteria. ⁴ (Information Commissioner’s Office)
Machine learning	A set of approaches within AI where statistical techniques and data are used to “teach” computer systems how to perform particular tasks, without these systems being explicitly programmed to do so. (SIENNA D4.1, p. 11.)

Table 2: Glossary of terms

⁴ <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/individual-rights/rights-related-to-automated-decision-making-including-profiling/>

1. Introduction

France is a semi-presidential Republic. The current Republic is the fifth one and started on 4 October 1958 with a new Constitution. The Parliament, composed of the National Assembly (made of 577 deputies) and the Senate (made of 348 senators), holds the legislative power. Sources of law in France are international and European treaties and conventions, constitutional and legislative rules, statutory instruments, and case laws.⁵ The highest juridical norm is the Constitution⁶ which is composed of three fundamental instruments: the Constitution of the 4 October 1958, the Declaration for the rights of man and citizen of 1789, and the Preamble to the Constitution of 27 October 1946.⁷ Since 1958, there have been 22 constitutional laws, i.e. laws that modify the constitution. Since 1971, the Constitutional council (*Conseil constitutionnel*) ensures that new laws conform with the Constitution.

France is subject to international law obligations and is a signatory to numerous international treaties and conventions, notably the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). According to Art. 55 of the French Constitution, international treaties ratified by France are superior to domestic legislation. Depending on the treaty at stake, it is either directly applicable to French law or needs to be transposed by an internal rule. As a member of the UN since its creation in 1945, France has signed several UN treaties of relevance to the regulation of AI and robotics, including the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)⁸ and the International Covenant on Social, Economic and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)⁹, both accessed on 4 November 1980. France is a founding member of the Council of Europe that drafted the ECHR, ratified by France on 3 May 1974.¹⁰ Finally, as a member of the European Union, it is subject to the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) of the European Parliament and the Council of Europe, in effect from 25 May 2018.¹¹ This Regulation is of particular relevance to the regulation of AI and robotics.

The position in France is that there is no AI and robotics-specific legislation. For the time being, existing laws and regulations cover these technologies, including any harms resulting from them, in particular the law n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 regarding information technology, files and liberties. This law has been modified several times since its establishment, most recently by the law n°2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 that integrates the EU GDPR with national legislation.¹²

⁵ For more details about the French legal system, sources of law, and legislative process, see: https://e-justice.europa.eu/content_member_state_law-6-fr-en.do?member=1.

⁶ Constitution of the French Republic, accessible on the page of the National Assembly: http://www.assemblee-nationale.fr/connaissance/constitution.asp#P1_42

⁷ Preamble to the Constitution of 27 October 1946, accessible on the page of the Constitutional Council: https://www.conseil-constitutionnel.fr/sites/default/files/as/root/bank_mm/anglais/cst3.pdf. To this should also be added the Environment Charter of 2004, also accessible on the page of the Constitutional Council: https://www.conseil-constitutionnel.fr/sites/default/files/as/root/bank_mm/anglais/charter_environnement.pdf

⁸ UN Treaty Collection, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) and list of countries that are parties to the Covenant: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=IND&mtmsg_no=IV-3&chapter=4&clang=en

⁹ UN Treaty Collection, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and list of countries that are parties to the Covenant : https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?chapter=4&clang=en&mtmsg_no=IV-4&src=IND

¹⁰ Council of Europe, European Convention on Human Rights: <https://www.echr.coe.int/Pages/home.aspx?p=basictexts/convention>. France Diplomatie, France and the European Court of Human Rights: <https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/en/french-foreign-policy/international-justice/european-court-of-human-rights/>

¹¹ Official Journal of the European Union, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN>

¹² The law may be accessed on the Legifrance website at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000886460>

The **objective** of this report is to review the state of the law and current legal responses to technological developments in AI and robotics and determine how specific questions and issues are addressed in France. It also introduces key aspects of the on-going French debate on the legal regulation of these technologies in the current legal academic literature. Considering the very rapid developments under study here, both in terms of technology and regulatory frameworks, this report focuses on developments within the last five to ten years.

The primary **method used** to prepare this report was desk research. The authors of this report used various search engines to obtain an overview of the issues being researched. General search engines such as Google were used along with more specific academic catalogues, notably the site Dalloz that brings together all legal literature produced in France. Parliamentary reports that have been published over the past few years have also been a useful resource. Another particularly valuable resource was the website - www.legifrance.gouv.fr - that gives access to all legal instruments currently applicable in France, as well as links to some translated versions of these documents.¹³

Over the past few years, AI and robotics have generated much interest from policymakers, regulators, and legal experts in France. A number of significant reports have been published on this topic by major French institutions. These touch, to varying degrees, upon questions of the legal regulation of these technologies. These reports include:

Council of State (*Conseil d'état*):

- "Public power and digital platforms: accompanying 'uberisation'" (*"Puissance publique et plateformes numériques: accompagner l'ubérisation"*), 2017.¹⁴
- "The digital and fundamental rights" (*"Le numérique et les droits fondamentaux"*), 2014.¹⁵

Parliamentary office for the evaluation of scientific and technological choices:

- "Toward a Controlled, Useful and Demystified Artificial Intelligence" (*"Pour une intelligence artificielle maîtrisée, utile et démystifiée"*), March 2017.¹⁶
- "Robots and the law" (*"Les robots et la loi"*), March 2016, no 3551.¹⁷

Reports commissioned by the government:

- Cédric Villani (MP), "Giving a sense to artificial intelligence. For a national and European strategy" (*"Donner un sens à l'intelligence artificielle. Pour une stratégie nationale et européenne"*), March 2018.¹⁸
- CGE (General Council for Economy), "Regulation of content processing algorithms" (*"Modalités de régulation des algorithmes de traitement de contenus"*), May 2016.¹⁹

¹³ Website of Legifrance : <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr>

¹⁴ Council of State: <http://www.conseil-etat.fr/Decisions-Avis-Publications/Etudes-Publications/Rapports-Etudes/Etude-annuelle-2017-Puissance-publique-et-plateformes-numeriques-accompagner-l-uberisation>

¹⁵ Document can be accessed from: <http://www.ladocumentationfrancaise.fr/rapports-publics/144000541/index.shtml>

¹⁶ Parliamentary office for the evaluation of scientific and technological choices: <https://www.senat.fr/notice-rapport/2016/r16-464-1-notice.html> and a synthesis report in English: <https://www.senat.fr/rap/r16-464/r16-464-syn-en.pdf>

¹⁷ Parliamentary office for the evaluation of scientific and technological choices: <https://www.senat.fr/notice-rapport/2015/r15-570-notice.html>

¹⁸ AI for Humanity: https://www.aiforhumanity.fr/pdfs/MissionVillani_Presse_FR-VF.pdf

¹⁹ Pavel, Ilarion and Jacques Serris, *Modalités de Régulation Des Algorithmes de Traitement de Contenus*, Paris, 13 May 2016. <https://www.economie.gouv.fr/cge/modalites-regulation-des-algorithmes-traitement-des-contenus>.

Significant academic publications on the legal regulation of AI and robotics published in the past five to ten years, include in particular:²⁰

- Bensamoun, A., "Des robots et du droit...", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2016, p. 281.
- Bensamoun, A., (ed.) *Les Robots. Objects scientifiques, objets de droits*, Sceaux, Mare & Martin, 2016.
- Bensoussan, A. and Bensoussan, J. *Droit des robots*, Paris, Larcier, 2015.
- Chatila, R., "Intelligence artificielle et robotique : un état des lieux en perspective avec le droit", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2016, p. 284.
- Choné-Grimaldi, A.-S. and P. Glaser, "Responsabilité civile du fait du robot doué d'intelligence artificielle : faut-il créer une personnalité robotique ?", *Contrats Concurrence Consommation*, no. 1, 2018.
- Courtois, G., "Robot et responsabilité", in A. Bensamoun (ed.), *Les Robots. Objects scientifiques, objets de droits*, Sceaux, Mare & Martin, 2016, pp. 129–156.
- Delage, P.-J., "Le statut juridique du robot", in Labbé, X. (ed), *L'homme augmenté face au droit*, Villeneuve d'Ascq, Presses Universitaires du Septentrion, 2015, pp. 51–62.
- Gautier, P.-Y., "De la propriété des créations issues de l'intelligence artificielle", *La Semaine Juridique*, vol. 37, p. 913, 2018.
- Larrieu, J., "La Propriété intellectuelle et les robots", *Journal International de Bioéthique*, vol. 24, no. 4, 2013, pp. 125–133.
- Malgieri, G., "Right to Explanation and Algorithm Legibility in the EU Member States Legislations", 2018, SSRN. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3233611
- Nevejans, N., *Traité de droit et d'éthique de la robotique civile*, Bordeaux, LEH Edition, 2017.

2. Scope and limitations of the report

The scope of this report is demarcated by the SIENNA task 4.2 workplan. It does not comprehensively cover all aspects of AI and robotics (given that both of these are vast topics in themselves, spanning a range of applications and sectors) regulation and all legal issues arising from such technologies, but has taken up for study a limited range of topics with high policy and human rights significance.

A challenge that the researchers faced in producing this report is the fact that AI and robotics technologies are not regulated by one specific law. The most relevant law is the n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 regarding information technology, files and liberties, as modified by the law 2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 that integrates the GDPR within national legislation. The challenge with current regulation of AI and robotics in France is due to the large variety of sectors within which they apply, as highlighted by the SIENNA Handbook.²¹ The different fields of application imply different regulations.

In addition, the very rapid developments of these technologies over the past five to 10 years is making legal regulation rapidly obsolete.²² Furthermore, an expert legal analysis is not yet available for some

²⁰ Please note that sometimes only one page number appears in the reference for articles. This is the way French legal academic articles are generally referenced. It is to be understood as "this page and the following".

²¹ SIENNA, D1.1: *The consortium's methodological handbook*, 30 April 2018, Section 4.

²² Bensamoun and Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

key pieces of law. This is particularly the case for the law mentioned above (n° 2018-493) for which it has been difficult to find academic articles reflecting upon this law as it was published in 21 June 2018.

Another challenge in producing this report was that experts in French law do not all agree with the definition of a robot. The key element of disagreement concerns whether a system requires a physical component in order to be recognised as a robot. For instance, Pierre-Yves Gautier talks about AI as a robot.²³ According to Alexandra Bensamoun and Grégoire Loiseau, AI in legal categories may be physical or not.²⁴ They disagree as such with the definition proposed by the European Parliament in the Resolution of the 16 February 2017 (pt 1) which recognises the robot as having “at least a minor physical support”. According to them, this definition of a robot is “excessively reductive”, considering the fact that an AI can exist without a physical component, such as a bot or an algorithm.²⁵ On the contrary, in her *Treaty of the law and the ethics of civil robotics*, Nathalie Nevejans defines a robot as a physical entity.²⁶ This is also the approach that the present report supports, in line with the SIENNA State-of-the-art Review on AI and robotics (D4.1).²⁷

3. Legal developments

This section examines legal developments pertaining to AI and robotics covering the last five to ten years.

Have developments in AI (i.e., automated decision-making systems, algorithmic systems, machine learning) and robotics led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights?

Developments in AI and robotics have generated much interest from policymakers and regulators in France. However, this has not led to any modification of the Constitution itself which has had only 22 revisions since it was proclaimed in 1958. Some legal developments with relevance to fundamental rights are highlighted below.

Have there been/are there attempts or plans to create or adopt new legislation in response to developments in AI and robotics (e.g., granting legal personhood to robots, prescribing civil or criminal liability for harms caused), or to regulate²⁸ how AI and robotics applications are designed, set up, commissioned or used? (e.g., regulation of algorithmic development or restrictions on the use of robots in certain conditions or sectors).

Though there is no specific national legislation on AI and robotics, a number of existing laws already address some of the key legal issues posed by these technologies. However, as the National Council for Informatics and Liberties (CNIL) and the legal expert Alexandra Bensamoun note, these are often

²³ Gautier, Pierre-Yves, "De La Propriété Des Créations Issues de l'intelligence Artificielle", *La Semaine Juridique*, 37, 2018, p. 913.

²⁴ Bensamoun and Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Nevejans, Nathalie, *Traité de Droit et d'éthique de La Robotique Civile*, Bordeaux, 2017.

²⁷ SIENNA, D4.1: *State-of-the-art Review, AI & Robotics*, 13 April 2018.

²⁸ This could be to restrict or advance the development or use of such applications.

disregarded in the French debate on the regulation of AI and robotics.²⁹ This report briefly highlights them below.

The main applicable law is the law n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 regarding information technology, files and liberties, as modified by the law 2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 to integrate the GDPR within national legislation.³⁰ According to Article 1 of this law: “Information technology must be at the service of each citizen. Its development must be carried out within the framework of international cooperation. It should not jeopardise human identity or breach human rights, privacy or individual or public liberties.”³¹ Since its creation, this law has been modified several times, including by:

- A reform in 2004;
- The law for a Digital Republic, law n° 2016-1321 of the 7 October 2016;
- The law n° 2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 which made use of the “margin of manoeuvre” conferred by the 27 April 2016 Directive (EU) 2016-679 to implement the directive within national law.³²

Finally, a new law on informatics technology and liberties is expected to be ordered by the government a few months after the creation of law 2018-493 in June 2018. However, this had not been done yet at the time of the writing of this report. The objective of this law would be to bring more coherence to the regulation on Information Technology (IT) and liberties as contained in the existing law.³³

Legal experts also recognise that the fundamental principles enshrined in the law on IT and Liberties are well-suited to address legal issues related to robotics, in particular the principles of consent (art. 7) and of forbidding automatic decisions that have significant implications, and the protection of private data (art. 34).³⁴

Another noteworthy legal development is the Law n°2015-992 of 17 August 2015³⁵ on energy transition for green growth (Energy Transition Law) that enabled the Government to allow fully or partially autonomous vehicles on the roads for experimentation (art. 37).³⁶

Are there new regulatory bodies being set up to regulate AI and robotics? What are the developments on this front? (e.g., AI watchdogs, AI commission, Robotics commission)

²⁹ National Council for Informatics and Liberties (CNIL), *Comment Permettre à l'homme de Garder La Main? Les Enjeux Éthiques Des Algorithmes et de l'intelligence Artificielle* (December 2017), p. 45. Alexandra Bensamoun, "Rapport de La CNIL Sur l'intelligence Artificielle: Une Réflexion Éthique", *Revue Pratique de La Prospective et de l'innovation*, 1, 2018, paragraph 18.

³⁰ The law may be accessed on the Legifrance website at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT00000886460>

³¹ Author's unofficial translation. Original in French: “l'informatique doit être au service de chaque citoyen. Son développement doit s'opérer dans le cadre de la coopération internationale. Elle ne doit porter atteinte ni à l'identité humaine, ni aux droits de l'homme, ni à la vie privée, ni aux libertés individuelles ou publiques.”

³² French government's legal portal, law n° 2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 relative to the protection of personal data https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do;jsessionid=AF9F76D628E3822E5D2A1F5A2B83791B.tplgfr27s_2?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000037085952&dateTexte=20180621

³³ CNIL website: <https://www.cnil.fr/fr/entree-en-vigueur-de-la-nouvelle-loi-informatique-et-libertes>

³⁴ Geffray, Edouard, "Quelle Protection Des Données Personnelles Dans l'univers de La Robotique?", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2016, p. 295.

³⁵ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000031044385&categorieLien=id>

³⁶ Bensamoun and Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

A number of regulatory bodies on AI and robotics have recently been put in place or already existing ones have been given extended responsibilities in relation to the regulation of AI and/or robotics.

The **National Commission of Informatics and Liberties (CNIL)** ensures the protection of personal data in France. Its responsibilities as defined in art. 11 of the n°78-17 law have been extended following the n°2016-1231 law for a Digital Republic. These include responsibility for carrying out a reflection on the ethical and social issues raised by the evolution of the digital technologies.³⁷

Following a recommendation in the report published by the General Council of Economy (CGE) in 2016, the State secretariat to digital economy gave the **National Research Institute in informatics technology and automatic systems (INRIA)** the role of operator of the scientific platform for the evaluation of the responsibility and transparency of algorithms.³⁸ In this task, INRIA is supported by the Institut Mines Télécom (IMT)³⁹ and the National Digital Council (CNNum).⁴⁰ The platform “TransAlgo” led by INRIA and launched in January 2017 brings together researchers from various institutions to evaluate the responsibility and transparency of algorithms.⁴¹

Furthermore, it is important to note that **CERNA (Commission for the reflection on the ethics of research in digital sciences and technologies of Allistene)** is promoting the creation of a **national ethics committee for the digital sector**, in the same way that there exists a national ethics committee for life and health sciences (National consultative committee for life and health sciences, the CCNE). However, this body has not yet been created.⁴²

The SYMOP (the Union of machines and production technologies) has called for the creation of a national ethics committee for robotics composed of jurists, sociologists, industrialists, scientists, and ethicists to monitor robotics.⁴³

Identify any significant case law or judgments⁴⁴ addressing human rights challenges⁴⁵ of AI and robotics (if there are no judgments, you can refer to legal doctrine)

Three recent judgements are of particular relevance to the issues at stake in this report.

Firstly, in the judgement n° 625 of the 19 June 2013, the court of appeal (*Cour de cassation*) judged that Google could not be held responsible for the words proposed on the basis of an algorithm that it had produced considering the strictly “automatic nature” of its functioning. What was at stake in this judgement was the function of *Google Suggest* that automatically suggests terms when carrying out a

³⁷ Bensamoun, Alexandra and Grégoire Loiseau, "La Gestion Des Risques de l'intelligence Artificielle. De l'éthique à La Responsabilité", *La Semaine Juridique*, 2017, p. 46.

³⁸ Pavel and Serris, op. cit., 2016.

³⁹ Institut Mines-Télécom: <https://www.imt.fr>. It is an institute that brings together engineering and management schools.

⁴⁰ Conseil national du numérique. <https://cnumerique.fr>.

⁴¹ Ganay, Claude De, and Dominique Gillot, *Report by the Parliamentary Office for the Evaluation of Scientific and Technological Choices. Toward a Controlled, Useful and Demystified Artificial Intelligence* (15 March 2017), 150. TransAlgo website: <https://www.inria.fr/actualite/actualites-inria/transalgo>

⁴² Collective of manager of scientific institutes, 'Il Faut Créer Un Comité National d'éthique Du Numérique', *Le Monde*, 14 December 2017. http://www.lemonde.fr/acces-restraint/idees/article/2017/12/14/a3e4925ad209014684789d00bb4bd126_5229661_3232.html.

⁴³ Bensoussan, Alain, and Renaud Champion, *Droit de La Robotique. Livre Blanc*, 2016, p. 81.

⁴⁴ Limited only to decisions in the highest courts – unless going further in depth is warranted.

⁴⁵ For example, discrimination, inequality, privacy infringements, unfavourable work conditions, harm to life, bodily integrity, human safety and welfare, liability etc.

search. The case was brought to court by an insurance company, the *Lyonnaise de garantie*. The company had found that, when doing a Google search with its name, the search engine would automatically suggest terms such as “crook” (“*escroc*”). However, the court held that, considering the automatic nature of the process, the algorithms, and behind them, Google, could not be held responsible for the terms suggested.⁴⁶

The White paper (*Livre blanc*) of the SYMOP on robotics law (“*Droit de la robotique*”) highlights how the court of appeal (*Cour de cassation*) has identified the responsibility of the employers in the case of breaches of the legislation relating to the security of workers in the use of robots. There have been two judgements by the Court. The first one relates to the death of a worker in a packaging factory (judgement n°02-87666 of the 30 September 2003 of the penal chamber of the court of appeal). The second concerns an employee on an automated production line. It has been shown that the employer did not take the necessary security measures (judgement n°01-21192 of the 16 September 2003 of the second civil chamber of the court of appeal).⁴⁷ Hence, in both cases, the court of appeal held the employer responsible for violating the law related to the security of employees working in automated systems.

Highlight any other relevant, potential future legal developments relating to AI and robotics identified in authoritative legal sources in your country

Following the integration of Regulation (EU) 2016/679⁴⁸ and Directive (EU) 2016/680⁴⁹ in June 2018, a new law was to be requested by the Government in the six months that followed.⁵⁰ It is not expected that this law will bring new elements to the already existing one but would primarily aim at making the IT and liberties law (n°78-17) more coherent now that it has gone through a series of revisions since its first draft in 1978.

Another potential future legal development of relevance includes the suggestion made by Alex Türk, former president of the CNIL (National Council for Information Technology and Liberties), to include the protection of personal data in the preamble of the French Constitution.⁵¹

Major reports recently published in France also point to some key legislative developments relevant to the regulation of AI and robotics. In particular, the report by the Parliamentary office for the evaluation of scientific and technological choices, “Toward a Controlled, Useful and Demystified Artificial Intelligence” (“*Pour une intelligence artificielle maîtrisée, utile et démystifiée*”) published in

⁴⁶ De Ganay, Claude de and Dominique Gillot, *Report by the Parliamentary Office for the Evaluation of Scientific and Technological Choices. Toward a Controlled, Useful and Demystified Artificial Intelligence*, 2017, pp. 156–57. <https://www.senat.fr/rap/r16-464/r16-464-syn-en.pdf>. See also Zerrouki, Abed, “Google n’est pas responsable des associations réalisées par Google Suggest”, *Droit du.net*, July 2013. <https://droitdu.net/2013/07/google-suggest-nest-pas-responsable-des-injures-associees-a-ses-propositions/>

⁴⁷ De Ganay and Gillot, *op. cit.*, 2017 p. 158.

⁴⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data

⁴⁹ Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data

⁵⁰ The present report was finished after the end of the 6-month period; however, no new law had been put in place by the time of the completion of this report.

⁵¹ Julien Bonnet and Pauline Türk, “Le Numérique: Un Défi Pour Le Droit Constitutionnel”, *Les Nouveaux Cahiers Du Conseil Constitutionnel*, 57/4, 2017, pp. 21–22.

March 2017 warns against the implementation of too strict legal constraints that would impede research in AI.⁵²

Another major, recently produced report on AI, i.e., the Villani report, makes a series of recommendations for the regulation of AI.⁵³ The most relevant of these to the present report is the suggestion to put in place zones in which legal constraints are loosened in order to encourage research and innovation in AI.⁵⁴ One key issue it raises is that current legislation focuses on individual protection of rights and liberties but misses the effects of this technology on the collective. In order to fill this gap, it advocates for the creation of collective rights on data.⁵⁵ Other regulatory recommendations made in this report include that of opening the “black box” of AI⁵⁶ and that of integrating ethical concerns right from the initial development of automated systems.⁵⁷

Furthermore, we expect that the Constitutional council will soon take a stance in relation to a right of dereferencing (*droit de déréférencement*), a development from the right to be forgotten recognised by the EU Court of justice since 2014.⁵⁸

4. Specific legal issues

This section explores selected specific legal issues related to AI and robotics. We explore and elaborate, for AI, two critical issues:

- Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems), i.e., how does the law deal with issues of algorithmic bias and discrimination?
- Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI i.e., does the law ascribe intellectual property rights (e.g., copyright, patent right, design rights, trademarks etc.) for AI generated works or inventions? Who owns such intellectual property rights?

For robotics, we will explore:

- Creation of a specific legal status for robots i.e., legal personhood or electronic personality, i.e., has the law created/does the law recognise a specific legal status for robots? Are there any movements in this direction?
- Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

⁵² De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 205–6.

⁵³ Cédric Villani, *Donner Un Sens à l'intelligence Artificielle. Pour Une Stratégie National et Européenne*, Paris, 2018.

⁵⁴ Villani, op. cit., 2018, p. 15.

⁵⁵ Villani, op. cit., 2018, pp. 148–49.

⁵⁶ Villani, op. cit., 2018, pp. 140–145.

⁵⁷ Villani, op. cit., 2018, pp. 146–148.

⁵⁸ Bonnet and Türk, "Le Numérique: Un Défi Pour Le Droit Constitutionnel", op. cit., 2017, p. 21–22.

4.1. Artificial intelligence

4.1.1. Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems)

Since its creation in 1978, the IT and liberties law addresses issues related to what was identified in the first version of this law text, as “automated treatment” of personal data (art. 5 of the law n° 78-17). With the massive technological developments that have occurred since this law was first written, the law has evolved to better regulate automated decision-making systems. In particular, since the law n°2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 that adapted the GDPR to French law, the risks of algorithmic bias and discrimination are better addressed. As Gianclaudio Malgieri puts it regarding the implementation of the GDPR in France, France can be seen as “proactive” in relation to the way it regulated automated decision-making, in particular in Art. 22(2).⁵⁹ According to the legal expert, French law is “one of the most innovative and complex regulations of automated decision-making.” It “adopts a very wide approach: it is not limited to decisions ‘which have legal effects (...) or similarly significantly affects’ the data subject.” Hence, “data controllers need to take specific safeguards when using any automated decision-making producing any ‘significant effect’.”⁶⁰

A specificity of the French implementation of GDPR is the fact that it regulates automated decision-making differently depending on the context in which these decisions are taken. It confers different degrees of protection and prohibition depending on whether it takes place in the judicial context, the administrative context or other contexts in which decisions have legal or other significant effects.⁶¹ As Malgieri puts it, according to the law n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 as amended by the law n°2018-493 of the 20 June 2018:⁶²

- “For *judicial decision* there is a total prohibition of automated decision, even if semi-automated.” (p. 16)⁶³
- “For *administrative decisions* there is a difference between semi-automated decisions and fully automated decisions. Fully automated decisions are prevented within administrative appeal [...]. Other kinds of administrative decisions are permitted, even if fully or partially automated, under certain conditions”, which Malgieri specifies on p. 16. (Art. 10)
- Finally, “for *private decisions*, no decision which as legal effects or that significantly affects a person can be taken solely on the basis of automated processing of personal data, including profiling”. (Art. 10) There are two exceptions to these which Malgieri mentions on p. 17.

It is important to note that there is also a special provision regulating automated decisions in education.⁶⁴ In this regards, as Malgieri notes, “a specific Ethics and Scientific Committee (mentioned

⁵⁹ Malgieri, Gianclaudio, "Right to Explanation and Algorithm Legibility in the EU Member States Legislations", *SSRN*, 2018, 9. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3233611

⁶⁰ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018, p. 17.

⁶¹ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018. pp. 15–16.

⁶² Malgieri, op. cit., 2018. pp. 16–17.

⁶³ Article 10. Article in French: “Aucune décision de justice impliquant une appréciation sur le comportement d'une personne ne peut avoir pour fondement un traitement automatisé de données à caractère personnel destiné à évaluer certains aspects de la personnalité de cette personne.” Available at <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT00000886460>

⁶⁴ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018, p. 17.

in the Education Code) shall submit each year, at the end of the national pre-registration procedure and before December, a report to the Parliament on this procedure and on the procedures for examining applications by higher education institutions. The committee may make any proposal on this occasion to improve the transparency of this procedure.”⁶⁵

Furthermore, as Malgieri points out, “there is no reference to the right to contest/challenge the decision, and to the subject’s right to express his/her view” (Art. 22(3) GDPR), nor is there “reference to the right to obtain human intervention”.⁶⁶ However, Art. 10 of the French law “is the first case in which the law guarantees a *right to explanation* (as mentioned at recital 71 of the GDPR) – or better a right to *legibility* – of algorithmic decisions! Data subjects have a right to receive, upon request, specific information about the main features of the *implementation* of the algorithmic data processing involving them.”⁶⁷

4.1.2. Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI

Intellectual property (IP) in France is regulated by a number of international treaties and multilateral agreements. In particular, France is a party to the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property of 20 March 1883 and the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works of 9 September 1886, and a member of regional instruments such as European Patent Convention that entered into force in 13 December 2007.⁶⁸ Intellectual property law in France is codified in the Intellectual Property Code.⁶⁹ IP rights in France primarily include: utility patents, designs, trademarks and authors’ rights.⁷⁰

In the current state of French IP law, the recognition of an AI as fully responsible for a particular creation does not exist and only human beings can benefit from the intellectual property regime.⁷¹ There are however some legal experts that support the recognition of autonomous systems as subjects of rights, in particular Alain Bensoussan whose position is developed more in-depth in the following section. Nonetheless, few experts support this position. In the major part of the literature that the authors of this report have explored, author’s right is recognised to apply only to human beings. In particular, this is the position of the rapporteurs of the 2017 Parliamentary report.⁷²

For Alexandra Bensamoun, in the current state of technological developments, AI is still a simple “tool”; no intellectual property right can be conferred to an AI system.⁷³ For Pierre-Yves Gautier, only a physical person can be recognised as an author (in France, the author is not a juridical fiction as it may be in other countries). According to Gautier, considering that even a “legal person” such as a company cannot be recognised as an author, it would be even more illegitimate to recognise this status

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018.

⁶⁷ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018, pp. 17–18.

⁶⁸ Roux-Vaillard, Stanislas, “France”, in Robert Baechtold, (ed.) *The Intellectual Property Review*, London, Law Business Research, 2016. <https://thelawreviews.co.uk/edition/the-intellectual-property-review-edition-5/1136639/france>

⁶⁹ The Legifrance website provides a translation of legislative and regulatory parts of the Intellectual Property Code into English : <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/Traductions/en-English/Legifrance-translations>.

⁷⁰ These different IP rights are briefly exposed in Roux-Vaillard, Stanislas, op. cit., 2016.

⁷¹ De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 145–46; Bensamoun, Alexandra, “Création et Données: Différence de Notions = Différence de Régime?”, *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2018, p. 85.

⁷² De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 145–46.

⁷³ Bensamoun, “Création et Données: Différence de Notions = Différence de Régime?”, op. cit., 2018, p. 85.

for an “immaterial object” such as a software.⁷⁴ This is also the view of the jurist Jacques Larrieu for whom the author’s right hardly fits the situation of an AI’s production (he talks about automated systems, which includes AI), in particular because the expression of a personality that is required for the application of this right is absent. Bensamoun and Loiseau also insist on the intrinsic link in French law between the human being, i.e., the physical person and the creation.⁷⁵

On the basis of the overview of the current literature on this topic, we can highlight three different solutions proposed by experts to regulate the intellectual property of products developed from AI:

- The contractual solution:
 - o This solution is supported by the lawyer Laurent Szuskin who proposes a distributive application of intellectual property.⁷⁶ For instance:
 - an invention by an AI system may be protected by a patent;
 - software may be protected by author’s rights;
 - databases may be protected by the specific law that applies to them, i.e. the law no 98-536 of 1 July 1998 on the protection of databases.⁷⁷
 - o This contractual solution is also upheld by Alexandra Bensamoun and Grégoire Loiseau.⁷⁸
- The solution that follows the logic of ‘offspring’ or ‘fruits’:
 - o Pierre-Yves Gautier proposes resorting to the regulation of certain objects such as animals⁷⁹, trees or money that are not recognised as subjects of rights but that produce value. The argument is: certain objects produce other objects, such as an animal produces offspring or a tree produces fruits. The owner of the first object becomes the owner of the second object that is produced or develops from the first. Gautier concludes from this argument that, in the case of a work produced by a software, the author of the software and the person who provided it with the data, both own the work produced.⁸⁰
- The solution through patent’s law, with inspiration from UK law:
 - o Jacques Larrieu (a professor of law) turns to patent law for the protection of the intellectual property of creations by these systems (art. L. 611-10 of the code of intellectual property). He proposes that French law takes inspiration from the 1988 Copyright, Designs and Patents Act (CDPA) according to which computer-generated works could be protected by copyright.⁸¹

Though there may be other approaches or solutions proposed in the French legal debate, these are the main ones that have been identified as part of the research conducted for preparing the present report.

⁷⁴ Gautier, op. cit., 2018, p. 913.

⁷⁵ Bensamoun Alexandra, and Grégoire Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans Certains Droits Spéciaux", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2017, p. 295.

⁷⁶ De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 145–46.

⁷⁷

Available

from:

<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000573438&dateTexte=&categorieLien=id>

⁷⁸ Bensamoun and Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", op. cit., p. 239.

⁷⁹ It is nonetheless important to recognise recent legal developments in relation to animals’ rights in French law. A new article of the Civil Code (art. 515-14) recognises them as “living and sentient beings”. Though this development may be perceived as opening a breach toward the recognition of a legal personality to animals, this is not yet the case in the current state of French law today. See for instance: <https://univ-droit.fr/la-gazette-juridique/18288-un-statut-de-l-animal-dans-le-code-civil>

⁸⁰ Gautier, op. cit., 2018, p. 913.

⁸¹ Larrieu, Jacques, "Robot et Propriété Intellectuelle", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2016, p. 291.

4.2. Robotics

4.2.1. Creation of a specific legal status for robots

The suggestion made by some experts to create a specific legal status for robots, is a key issue in the French debate related to the legal regulation of robots – as well as AI since, as mentioned in section 2 of this report, for some French jurists, the fact that there is a physical element or not is irrelevant. Before presenting the current state of the debate in France on this question, it is essential to clarify the fact that, French law only has two different categories of entities:

1. “*persona*”: persons, who are subjects of rights: this corresponds to the main category, or the principal one. There are two types of persons: the “physical person”, i.e., an individual human being and a “legal person” (called “*personne morale*” in French) such as a corporation.
2. “*res*”: things or objects: these fall in the secondary, residual category.

Whatever is not a person, is necessarily a thing.⁸²

One of the most vocal proponents of the creation of a specific legal status for robots in France is the lawyer Alain Bensoussan, an expert in the regulation of new technologies.⁸³ Bensoussan has advocated a legal status for robots since 2013.⁸⁴ He established the Association of the law of robots (“*Association du droit des robots*”)⁸⁵ to promote the creation of a specific juridical framework for robotics. According to him, this is a necessity considering the capacities, characterised by intelligence and autonomy, that robots have acquired recently due to technological developments.⁸⁶ For him, existing texts, such as the 1978 law does not give a juridical framework sufficient to respond to current technological developments, in particular in terms of machine learning, robot capacity to take decisions, and questions related to confidentiality of the data it collects.⁸⁷ He suggests adding to the two already categories of subject of right – the “physical person” (an individual) and the “legal person (such as a company) – that of the “person robot” (“*personne robot*”) for “intelligent robots”, i.e., robots that may be said to have a certain autonomy. The position defended by Alain Bensoussan is very close to that proposed in the 27 January 2017 Report with recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics (2015/2103(INL)).⁸⁸

Bensoussan proposes giving robots an identity number. According to Bensoussan, the robot holds a very special position in-between, on the one hand, persons, whether physical (the human person) or moral (a company for instance) and, on the other hand, objects.⁸⁹ To him, the fact that the robot may have some freedom due to the autonomy it has been conferred implies that it cannot be treated in the law like any other objects. According to him, this autonomy implies, as he puts it, a “paradigm

⁸² Delage, Pierre-Jérôme, “Le Statut Juridique Du Robot”, in *L’homme Augmenté Face Au Droit*, op. cit., 2015, p. 54.

⁸³ See for instance his 2015 TEDx talk in Paris, “De l’urgence des droits des robots?” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3qkjEeV3Sno>

⁸⁴ Bensoussan, Alain, “Réflexions Sur La Personne Robot”, *Planète Robots*, 52, 2018, pp. 16–17.

⁸⁵ Association of the law of robots (“*Association du droit des robots*”). <https://www.association-droit-robot.fr>

⁸⁶ Bensoussan, “Réflexions Sur La Personne Robot”, 2018, p. 17.

⁸⁷ De Ganay and Gillot, op.cit., 2017, pp. 143–44.

⁸⁸ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-//EP//TEXT+REPORT+A8-2017-0005+0+DOC+XML+V0//EN>

⁸⁹ Bensoussan, Alain, “Droit Des Robots : Science-Fiction Ou Anticipation ?”, op. cit., 2015, p. 1640.

shift⁹⁰ to which the legal system should adapt – one crucial aspect of this adaptation implies the recognition of the intelligent robot as a particular type of subject of right. Hence, Bensoussan proposes to extend the logic that has led to the recognition of “legal person” for companies or other types of collective enterprises, i.e., the recognition of a legal personality to non-human entities, to the intelligent robot.⁹¹ With this perspective in mind, he drafted a proposal for a charter of the rights of robots that gives these artificial entities a specific juridical personality and a right to dignity. His “right of robots” would have three axes: (1) general rules relevant to all types of robots, (2) specific rules per type of robot (such as autonomous vehicle, humanoid robot, etc.), (3) reference documents on robotic in relation to ethical, cultural, and normative aspects.⁹²

Other French experts are firmly against the creation of a specific legal status for robots. This is particularly the case for Alexandra Bensamoun who has extensively written on this topic. Loiseau and Bensamoun write that this idea “must be firmly rejected as it is as useless as it is dangerous.”⁹³ According to them, it is not justified in the current state of the technology considering that robots are still very limited in the tasks they may accomplish: they do not have generalist abilities as humans do and have no intentionality in their action. Bensamoun and Loiseau are also against the creation of a registration system for advanced robots as proposed by the European Parliament. According to them, this poses the question as to which objects this would apply. Plus, as they argue, it would not solve the issues related to security and responsibility (as developed further below). Recognising the robot as a subject of right, and not simply as an object, would profoundly disturb currently existing French juridical categories by bringing about a sort of “chimera”, half-person and half-object, between the object and the subject of right. To them, that would be a profound perversion of the “*summa divisio*” of the current legal system between persons and objects.⁹⁴

Xavier Labbée also strongly insists on the need to maintain this clear distinction within the law. Though he recognises that recent technological developments challenge it, he insists on the need to maintain this distinction as it is key in distinguishing the cyborg from the android. While, according to him, the cyborg remains a person, a subject of rights, i.e. a person protected by persons’ civil and criminal law, even if his/her body is composed of a set of various artificial materials, the android on the contrary, as sophisticated as it may be, is only an object protected by property law.⁹⁵ Similarly, for Pascal Labbée, the robot “will never have a legal personality... It is lacking the ‘soul’” which is what grants legal personality.⁹⁶

In spite of great technological developments of robotics, in particular the increasing autonomy of robots rendered possible by AI, the rapporteurs of the 2017 Parliamentary Report reject the idea of recognising a legal personality to the robot. They wonder what entity exactly should receive a juridical personality: the robot itself or its AI? In any case, as they put it, it is “urgent to wait in this matter”.⁹⁷

Pierre-Yves Gautier also does not support the idea of giving a specific juridical status to robots. According to him, there is not really a “juridical void” requiring the creation of new concepts, such as that of a new legal entity for the robot or for an AI. Existing juridical categories are sufficient to address

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 143–44.

⁹³ Bensamoun and Loiseau, “L’intégration de l’intelligence Artificielle Dans l’ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps”, op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ Labbée, Xavier, “L’androïde, Le Cyborg et Les Lois Bioéthiques”, *Les Petites Affiches*, 105, 2011, p. 7.

⁹⁶ Labbée, Pascal, “L’homme Augmenté à l’épreuve de La Distinction Des Personnes et Des Choses”, op. cit., 2015, p. 47. Quote in the original French language: “le robot n’aura jamais la personnalité juridique... Il lui manque l’âme”.

⁹⁷ De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, p. 144.

the issues at stake, such as that of intellectual property, which is one of those he addresses.⁹⁸ He is, as such, particularly critical of the European Parliament's resolution regarding the possibility of creating a legal entity for robots.⁹⁹

The debate related to the creation of a special legal status for robots is also directly related to the question of safety and civil liability of the robot addressed below. These two questions are intrinsically related as the proposition of creating special legal status for a robot is often justified by the need to ensure liability for any potential damages caused by the robot. However, Bensamoun and Loiseau disagree that liability issues would be better addressed with a specific legal status for the robot. According to them, this would partly remove the sense of responsibility on the part of the producer to ensure a safe product.¹⁰⁰ On the contrary, Anne-Sophie Choné-Grimaldi and Philippe Glaser challenge the idea that creating a specific legal status for robots would imply a loss of responsibility. They point to the fact that the status of a subject of right has already been conferred to non-human entities under the title of a 'legal person', (*personne morale*) and that this has not implied a loss of responsibility.¹⁰¹

4.2.2. Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

As mentioned above, in the current state of the French legal system, robots fall within the regulation of 'things' and depend on a 'subject of rights'. It is liability for the actions of things that is therefore at stake. However, considering current technical developments in robotics, the distinction between "objects" and "subjects" of rights is being challenged, leading some experts to promote the creation of a special legal status for robots (see Bensoussan's position presented above¹⁰²). This section presents the way safety and civil liability issues are handled in French law today and touches on some potential future developments as projected by some legal experts.

For some experts, such as the lawyer Georgie Courtois¹⁰³ and Bensamoun and Loiseau (whose position has already been mentioned above¹⁰⁴), it is too early, given the current state of technological developments, to promote the creation of a new regime conferring legal rights to robots. According to them, it is necessary to wait to see how practices evolve. Bensamoun and Loiseau agree with the European Parliament's Resolution of the 16 February 2017 according to which it will not be possible to establish a new legal framework for the next 10 to 15 years. In this period of transition, it is necessary to address arising issues with already existing laws.¹⁰⁵ Courtois points in particular to the liability for objects (as defined in art. 1384 of the Civil code) and points to the responsibility of the producer in case of a faulty object (as defined in art. 1386-4 of the Civil code).¹⁰⁶

With the increasing autonomy that robots are acquiring due to technological developments, the current approach of civil liability for robots is being challenged. With these evolutions in mind, Courtois suggests drawing from already existing liability regimes, in particular that related to liability for the

⁹⁸ Gautier, op. cit., 2018, p. 913.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Bensamoun and Loiseau, "La Gestion Des Risques de l'intelligence Artificielle. De l'éthique à La Responsabilité", op. cit., p. 46.

¹⁰¹ Choné-Grimaldi, Anne-Sophie, and Philippe Glaser, "Responsabilité Civile Du Fait Du Robot Doué d'intelligence Artificielle : Faut-Il Créer Une Personnalité Robotique ?", *Contrats Concurrence Consommation*, 1, 2018.

¹⁰² Bensoussan, Alain, "Droit Des Robots : Science-Fiction Ou Anticipation ?", op. cit., 2015, p. 1640.

¹⁰³ Courtois, Georgie, "Robot et Responsabilité" in Alexandra Bensamoun (ed.), *Les Robots. Objets Scientifiques, Objets de Droits*, Sceaux, 2016, pp. 129–156.

¹⁰⁴ Bensamoun and Loiseau, "L'intégration de l'intelligence Artificielle Dans l'ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps", op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid; Courtois, "Robot et Responsabilité", op. cit., 2016, p. 135.

¹⁰⁶ Courtois, op. cit., 2016, pp. 135–41.

action of a third person: liability for attendants (art. 1384 al. 5 of the Civil code), for children (art. 1384 al. 4 of the Civil code), or for animals (art. 1385 of the Civil code).¹⁰⁷ He also proposes drawing a parallel with liability related to motorized land vehicles (as defined in the Badinter law of the 5 July 1985).¹⁰⁸

As for Bensamoun and Loiseau, they point to the significance of insurance systems and the need to pay attention to the way these will evolve in relation to future technological developments in robotics. Indeed, as they note, “liability law has become, to a large extent, dependent upon insurance law”.¹⁰⁹ They also particularly insist on the responsibility of the producer when there is a security flaw in the system. As part of the focus on the responsibility of producers, they want to strengthen the duty of prevention.¹¹⁰

Bensamoun and Loiseau agree that, with regards to particular technologies it is important that regulatory frameworks are already put in place. This is for instance the case for autonomous vehicles for which, through the Law n° 2015-992 of the 17 August 2015 related to the energy transition, the Government is given the right to allow fully or partially autonomous vehicles on the roads for the sake of experimentation.¹¹¹

In any case, for Courtois, Bensamoun, Loiseau, and the rapporteurs of the 2017 parliamentary report, creating a specific legal status for robots as suggested by Bensoussan would not solve the issues related to safety and liability. For Bensoussan on the contrary, technological developments in robotics make it necessary to bring about a new legal system to ensure civil liability.¹¹²

5. Brief analysis of gaps and challenges

Finally, this report presents a brief analysis of gaps and challenges in the French legal regulation of AI and robotics and more generally on the state of the legal debate in France on the regulation of these technologies.

To begin with, the approach of regulating AI and robotics through ethical frameworks is being questioned in the French legal literature. This is an issue that Bensamoun and Loiseau in particular address.¹¹³ According to them, this approach might be pertinent. Indeed, ethics and soft laws are well-adapted to emerging technologies considering the rapidly changing nature of these objects and the need to prevent any barriers on technological developments. However, as Bensamoun notes, it is

¹⁰⁷ Courtois, op. cit., 2016, pp. 141–49. Bensamoun also mentions the possibility to adapt this regime of responsibility to robots characterised by a certain degree of autonomy. Alexandra Bensamoun, ‘Des Robots et Du Droit...’, *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2016, p. 281.

¹⁰⁸ Courtois, op. cit., 2016, pp. 141–49.

¹⁰⁹ Bensamoun and Loiseau, “L’intégration de l’intelligence Artificielle Dans l’ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps”, op. cit., 2017, p. 239. Original version in French: “Il nous semble en tout cas encore trop tôt, en l’état actuel des choses, pour profiler un régime plutôt qu’un autre. Les choix ne pourront être faits, au double point de vue juridique et économique, qu’avec le recul de l’expérience pratique. Il faut en particulier compter sur les orientations que prendront les systèmes assurantiels, lesquelles détermineront le point d’ancrage de la couverture du risque. On ne peut en effet ignorer que le droit de la responsabilité est devenu, dans une large mesure, le captif du droit des assurances.”

¹¹⁰ Bensamoun and Loiseau, “La Gestion Des Risques de l’intelligence Artificielle. De l’éthique à La Responsabilité”, op. cit., 2017, p. 46.

¹¹¹ Bensamoun and Loiseau, “L’intégration de l’intelligence Artificielle Dans l’ordre Juridique En Droit Commun: Questions de Temps”, op. cit., 2017, p. 239.

¹¹² Bensoussan, Alain and Jérémy Bensoussan, *Droit Des Robots*, Paris, 2015.

¹¹³ Bensamoun and Loiseau, “La Gestion Des Risques de l’intelligence Artificielle. De l’éthique à La Responsabilité”, op. cit., 2017, p. 46.

necessary to recognise the problem of the “weak normativity” that characterises these systems as well as the absence of sanctions.¹¹⁴ Soft regulation cannot replace the legislative response.

With regards to the legislative response, a key issue that remains open among French legal experts concern the question as to whether new developments in AI and robotics are generating a “juridical void”. Has it become necessary to create new concepts, in particular that of a new legal entity for AI and smart robots? Though there is significant disagreement among French legal experts on this question, the dominant perspective at the moment is the one according to which it is not yet the time to bring about a new legal entity to highly sophisticated automated systems. However, up to what point of technological development is this going to be the case? This is a point of tension that will require intense vigilance on the part of legal experts and policy-makers in the coming years.

More specifically, with regards to particular gaps in French law today, we may note, as the CNIL does, that the law tends to focus on the impact of digital technologies on the individual and often fails to take into account the collective effects of algorithms. As such, issues such as the “filter bubble” that generates algorithms and the related risks in terms of cultural pluralism tend to be neglected.¹¹⁵ This is also a point that the Villani report raises.¹¹⁶ On this point, the Villani report recommends the creation of collective rights on data.¹¹⁷

Another point of tension that may be highlighted in the French context is the one between the recognition of the need to protect privacy and personal data, while, at the same time, promoting the development of AI technologies that depend upon a large access to data.¹¹⁸

6. Conclusion

This report sought to review the state of the law and current legal responses to technological developments in AI and robotics and to determine how specific questions and issues are addressed in France. Currently, there is no specific law regulating AI or robotics in France. Nonetheless, some already existing laws address a number of key issues related to these technologies, in particular the law n°78-17 of the 6 January 1978 regarding information technology, files and liberties as modified by the law n°2018-493 of the 20 June 2018 that integrates the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) with national legislation. A new law on informatics technology and liberties was expected to be ordered by the government a few months after the creation of law 2018-493 in June 2018. However, this has not been done yet by the time of the writing of this report. The objective of this law would be to bring more coherence to the regulation on Information Technology (IT) and liberties as contained in the existing law.¹¹⁹

A specificity of the French implementation of GDPR is the fact that it regulates automated decision-making differently depending on the context in which these decisions are taken. It confers different

¹¹⁴ Alexandra Bensamoun, “Rapport de La CNIL Sur l’intelligence Artificielle: Une Réflexion Éthique”, *Revue Pratique de La Prospective et de l’innovation*, 1, 2018, para. 32.

¹¹⁵ National Council for Informatics and Liberties (CNIL), op. cit., 2017, pp. 34–39.

¹¹⁶ Villani, op. cit., 2018, pp. 148–49.

¹¹⁷ Ibid.

¹¹⁸ Villani, op. cit. 2018, p. 15.

¹¹⁹ CNIL website: <https://www.cnil.fr/fr/entree-en-vigueur-de-la-nouvelle-loi-informatique-et-libertes>

degrees of protection and prohibition depending on whether it takes place in the judicial context, the administrative context or other contexts in which decisions have legal or other significant effects.¹²⁰

Furthermore, the great interest shown by the French government for AI and robotics generates a concern to avoid too strict legal constraints that would impede research and development in these technologies.¹²¹ Due to recent technological developments in AI and robotics, regulatory/advisory bodies on AI and robotics such as the CNIL and INRIA have recently been given extended responsibilities in relation to the regulation of these technologies.

The question related to the legal status of autonomous systems is key in the current debate in France on the legal regulation of AI and robotics (it is addressed in Section 4.2.1 of the present report). This has in turn repercussions on the way intellectual property of AI is regulated (addressed in Section 4.1.2) as well as safety and civil liability issues (addressed in Section 4.2.2). At the moment, such status is not recognised and only a few legal experts are supporting the creation of this status. The majority of them believe that the *summa divisio* of French law between the subject of right and the object of right is not to be challenged for the time being.

¹²⁰ Malgieri, op. cit., 2018. pp. 15–16.

¹²¹ De Ganay and Gillot, op. cit., 2017, pp. 205–6.

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¹²² Please note that sometimes only one page number appears in the reference for articles ; this is indeed the way French legal academic articles are generally referenced. It is to be understood as "this page and the following".

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Annex

Term/text in original language (French)	English translation	Source of translation (official/unofficial/other)	Explanation, disclaimers
<i>Personne morale</i>	Legal person	Unofficial	This seems to be the most commonly accepted term in English.